

REFLECTIVE MODULE AND THE AFFECTIVE ELEMENTS IN SCIENCE LEARNING AMONG GRADE 7 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Science learners should be reflective, approach learning meaningfully, connect what they learn to previous experience, monitor their level of understanding of newly introduced concepts, and be able to express their feelings about what's being taught (Al – Rawani 2015). Reflective module in science can be one of the materials to be used to increase their learning ability. Thus, the researcher aimed to determine the impact of reflective module on students' learning of science in terms of receiving, responding, valuing, organizing and characterizing. This study used a quasi-experimental research participated by thirty-five students. Most of the students are 13 years old, male and female. Based on the experts and students, the reflective module is highly effective in the teaching learning process. However, the finding revealed that before exposing to the reflective module the level of students in science is apprentice. After using the reflective module they were at proficient level. This result suggests that the reflective module can be used as guide in exploring other ways of increasing learners' performance.

Keywords: Reflective Module, Affective Elements, Science Learning